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1. Abbreviations

CMR: Compact Membrane Reactor

CO: Confidential

D: Deliverable

DEM: Demonstrator

DoA: Description of the Action

DoW: Description of Work

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GA: Grant Agreement

GCW: Gross Combination Weight

HDV: Heavy Duty Vehicle

IPR Intellectual Property Rights

LH: Long Haul

M: Month

NG: Natural Gas

SCE: Single Cylinder Engine

ICE: Internal Combustion Engine

PC: Project Coordinator

PM: Project Manager

PO: Project Officer

PP: Program Participants

PU: Public

RD: Regional Delivery

RE: Restricted

SC: Steering Committee

SM: Sales Manager

SME: Small and Medium Enterprises

SQS: Seminal Quality System

T: Task

TM: Technical Manager

UD: Urban Delivery

WP: Work Package

2. Summary

This document summarizes the preliminary layout and sizing of a multi-fuel system, which main components are a compact membrane reactor (CMR) in combination with a fuel cell or an internal combustion engine (compare also Figure 1). A very wide range of fuels like ammonia, natural gas, biogas or alcohols feed the CMR and produces in this application hydrogen. The hydrogen is used for the internal combustion engine to produce mechanical power or for the fuel cell to produce electrical power with zero emissions.

Figure 1: Overall System Schematic

The objective of this deliverable is to perform a preliminary sizing of the entire system, consisting of the CMR & H₂ICE or alternatively CMR & FCS. Based on the power demand of the selected application and the expected in and out energy flows of each subsystem a preliminary sizing of each component can be performed.

As today's Trucks are mostly powered by ICE's, existing combustion engine data which are adapted for hydrogen fuel, define the required maximum system output power and the resulting necessary H₂ fuel flow delivered by the CMR.

The sizing of the Fuel-Cell System also follows the boundary conditions for the ICE, as similar requirements for peak-power and average power for defined routes are derived from the ICE-application. Thus the FCS and the ICE are directly comparable in terms of overall efficiency and TCO. Also the two overall systems (i.e. CMR & ICE vs. CMR & FCS) can be directly compared in terms of required space, overall energy demand and other KPIs later on.

3. System Sizing Based on Integrated System Application

3.1 Preliminary Sizing of the Compact Membrane Reactor

The preliminary CMR sizing for each application (H₂ICE and FCS) is based on the required maximum output power, input flows, and the number of cells/surface per cell.

Taking into account the maximum output power for FCS and H₂ICE estimated by our partners in CMT and AVL, respectively, a total electrochemical area of the CMR has been calculated for each case (see Table 1 and Table 2).

The H₂ generated, NH₃ demanded and the current density needed at 95% faradaic efficiency has been calculated for 3 possible situations: at low, medium and peak output power demand.

From these data a CMR volume estimation has been performed, taking into account commercial square cells of 12cm length from Elcogen¹ and hypothetical square cells of 20cm length. Besides, these calculations have been carried out considering the commercial solid-oxide-cell-stacks of 39 and 119 cells per stack nowadays available from Elcogen¹.

Table 1: CMR volume estimation for CMR-FCS case

CASE		CMR - FCS			
Electrochemical area	m²	80			
		low	medium	peak	
H ₂ generated	kg/h	2	5	10	
	Nm ³ /h	23	56	112	
NH ₃ demanded	kg/h	12	30	60	
Current density	A/cm²	0,0670	0,1675	0,3350	
Volume estimation					
Parameter\Case	units	1	2	3	4
Square cells					
Length	cm	12	12	20	20
Cell area	cm ²	144	144	400	400
Number of cells required		5556	5556	2000	2000
Cells per stack		39	119	39	119
Number of stacks		143	47	52	17
Stack dimensions					
L	mm	190	190	317	317
W	mm	315	230	527	385
H	mm	90	280	151	469
Volume per stack	L	5,39	12,24	25,23	57,24
Overall volume	m³	0,7703	0,5751	1,3117	0,9731

¹ See also: 1. <https://elcogen.com/products/solid-oxide-cell-stacks/>

Table 2: CMR volume estimation for CMR-H2ICE case

CASE		CMR - H2ICE			
Electrochemical area	m²	160			
		low	medium	peak	
H2 generated	kg/h	5	11	20	
	Nm ³ /h	56	124	224	
NH3 demanded	kg/h	30	66	120	
Current density	A/cm²	0,0838	0,1843	0,3350	
Volume estimation					
Parameter\Case	units	1	2	3	4
Square cells					
Length	cm	12	12	20	20
Cell area	cm ²	144	144	400	400
Number of cells required		11112	11112	4000	4000
Cells per stack		39	119	39	119
Number of stacks		285	94	103	34
Stack dimensions					
L	mm	190	190	317	317
W	mm	315	230	527	385
H	mm	90	280	151	469
Volume per stack	L	5,39	12,24	25,23	57,24
Overall volume	m³	1,5352	1,1502	2,5983	1,9461

3.2 Preliminary Sizing of the H₂ Internal Combustion Engine

For the sizing of the ICE, first the relevant boundary conditions must be defined. In the given case, these boundary conditions depend on the vehicle type and HD vehicle market situation.

The market for Heavy Duty Vehicles in Europe is diversified in terms of application / usage profile and vehicle layout. Figure 2 gives an overview of the share of different vehicle types in Europe in 2019. Dependent on application different vehicle types (Rigid vs. Tractor) and different axle configurations (e.g. 4x2, 6x2) are used. Within this context, a Configuration named T 4x2 stands for a Tractor application, with 4 wheels, whereas 2 wheels are driven.

It can be seen, that the vast majority of sold vehicles in Europe with a GCW >16t correspond to group no 5 for Long Haul transportation: A 4x2 tractor with a sleeper cab.

SUBGROUP SHARE

	Q3-Q4 share	Configuration	GCW [T]	Engine [kW]	Cabin	
	4-UD	0.4%	R 4x2	>16	<170	All
	4-RD	7.9%	R 4x2	>16	≥170 day cab ≥170 <265 sleeper cab	Day & sleeper
	4-LH	1.9%	R 4x2	>16	≥265	Sleeper
	5-RD	0.8%	T 4x2	>16	All-day cab <265 sleeper cab	Day & sleeper
	5-LH	62.8%	T 4x2	>16	≥265 sleeper cab	Sleeper
	9-RD	7.2%	R 6x2			Day
	9-LH	9.2%	R 6x2			Sleeper
	10-RD	0.1%	T 6x2			Day
	10-LH	9.7%	T 6x2			Sleeper

Figure 2: Sales Share of Trucks in Europe 2019²

Corresponding to Figure 2 another market study from 2016 (see also Figure 3) shows in addition also the corresponding total CO₂ share. Although the study is from 2017, the overall figures have remained relatively stable over the recent years. Following this study from the ICCT, equivalent to the majority of sales is related to vehicle category No. 5, also the total CO₂ share of this vehicle group is exceeding the combined CO₂ share of all other groups.

Consequently, when selecting the powertrain for the ALL-IN Zero Project, it should be derived from the vehicle group no.5 (Long Haul Tractor, 4x2) as this vehicle group has the biggest leverage on CO₂ emission reduction.

² From ACEA Paper: CO₂ emissions from heavy-duty vehicles – Preliminary CO₂ baseline (Q3-Q4 2019). https://www.acea.auto/files/ACEA_preliminary_CO2_baseline_heavy-duty_vehicles.pdf

Figure 3: Distribution of new HDV registrations and CO₂ emissions in the European Union in 2016³

Despite the initiatives from the EU and the recent developments of European truck manufacturers as of today, still the vast majority of sold trucks in the EU are powered by Diesel Engines. Figure 4 shows the distribution of sold engines by displacement from one major European truck OEM. Despite different approaches and different designs by each OEMs, the engine lineup is relatively homogeneous in Europe. The engines from each OEM can be roughly categorized into 4 groups:

- Small HD engines with a displacement of around 8l, mainly for smaller urban and regional delivery trucks.
- Medium HD engines with a displacement of 11l, used for all applications where the focus is on low upfront invest and maintenance cost.
- Mainstream HD engines with a displacement of 13l, used for all trucks, with overall best TCO and good performance.
- Large HD engines, with a displacement of >15l, used for special applications such as heavy-duty transport and prestige (e.g. fleet owners).

Following Figure 4 it can be seen, that the vast majority of sales can be accounted for the 13l engine class.

³ From: Fuel Efficiency Technology in European Heavy-Duty Vehicles: Baseline and Potential for the 2020–2030 Time Frame. ICCT White Paper. https://theicct.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/EU-HDV-Tech-Potential_ICCT-white-paper_14072017_vF.pdf

Figure 4: Number of sold HD engines from an European OEM within one year

Like for the engine displacement, the sold units can also be differentiated by engine power. Following Figure 5, most of the sold engines have a maximum power of 325-350kW. This power rating obviously delivers the best compromise between fuel-efficiency / cost and overall performance (i.e. transport times).

Figure 5: Number of sold engines over rated engine power from an European OEM within one year

Following the market situation above, the maximum output power for the single cylinder engine was defined for a typical 13l long haul engine in the range of 325kW.

Table 3: Engine Specs. for six-cylinder gas / six-cylinder hydrogen and derived single-cylinder hydrogen engine

Item	NG-6 Cyl.	H ₂ -6 Cyl.	H ₂ -SCE
Displacement [l]	12.9	12.9	2.147
Bore x Stroke [mm]	Ø135x150	Ø135x150	Ø135x150
Power [kW] @1900rpm	338	323.5	53.9
Spec. Power [kW/l]	26	25	25
BMEP [bar] @1100rpm	19.5	21.5	21.5
BTE [%] sweet spot	38	43	43
EGR System	w/o		with

Table 3 shows the initial specification of the H₂SCE, derived from the 6-cylinder Hydrogen engine which again is being derived from the 6-cylinder NG base engine. The estimated values for peak power, BTE, etc.. are derived from previous investigations @ AVL with another 6-cylinder H₂ engine in the same engine class⁴. As the research program continues it is expected that the current estimations might slightly change into the one or other direction due to the derived investigation results. However, in general the depicted performance figures should act well as initial information, also for the definition of the other parts of the overall system (i.e. CMR & H₂SCE).

Besides this main engine specs., for the sizing of the CMR and comparability of the FCS, cycle data for the H₂ engine have been generated. For instance some values of a hot WHTC can be found in Table 4:

Table 4: Hot WHTC results from six-cylinder Hydrogen Engine

WHTC hot	Average	Peak
Power [kW]	56	267
MF_FUEL [kg/h]	4.7	30
MF_IA [kg/h]	408	1629
MF_EXH [kg/h]	418	1645
T_EXH_EO [°C]	347	431

In addition, simulation data of a 40t vehicle equipped with the same engine can be provided for the driving cycles “Vecto” and “customer cycle”.

The related engine-speed and -torque traces together with the H₂ injection-mass flow can be found in Figure 6. Whilst the Vecto-cycle is highly relevant as it’s being used to declare the official fuel-consumption, the used customer cycle shows average performance and fuel-consumption for a typical drive cycle in Central-Europe.

⁴ See also: Arnberger, A., Grabner, P., Eder, M. *et al.* Hydrogen Combustion Engine for CO₂-neutral Commercial Vehicles. *ATZ Heavy Duty world* **14**, 36–41 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41321-021-0431-5>

Figure 6: Engine-speed and torque traces for two different drive-cycles (Vecto-cycle and customer-cycle)

In addition to the time-traces and average numbers for power and fuel-flow, Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the operating point distribution for the cycles in the engine map. It can be seen that most of the engine operation actually takes place only in a small band around 1000rpm and alongside the full load-curve. The Road-Load point (i.e. the point where the engine is powering the vehicle on a flat road at constant Highway speed) is between 600 and 800Nm, resp. at around 80kW. Naturally this is somewhat lower than the average power for both cycles, which is 97kW and 90kW respectively. Corresponding to this the average H₂ fuel flow for both cycles is calculated with 6.3kg/h and 6kg/h.

Figure 7: Engine Operating areas in the Vecto cycle

Figure 8: Engine Operating areas in the customer cycle

Besides the cycle results, the engine mapping results from AVL's six-cylinder Hydrogen engines can be found below (Figure 9 to Figure 13). The results from the engine testbed were also used as an input for the vehicle-cycle simulation as shown in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8. The mapping shows the measured results for the relevant inputs and outputs for the CMR sizing, such as:

- Required fuel mass flow; to be delivered by CMR
- Air mass flow
- Exhaust mass flow; used to calculate exhaust enthalpy; this energy could be used by the CMR
- Exhaust temperature; used to calculate exhaust enthalpy; this energy could be used by the CMR
- Coolant water enthalpy; this energy could be used by the CMR

Figure 9: Engine mapping - Hydrogen fuel mass flow

Figure 10: Engine mapping - Air mass flow

Figure 11: Engine mapping - Exhaust mass flow

Figure 12: Engine mapping - Engine Out Exhaust Gas Temperature

Figure 13: Engine mapping - Coolant Enthalpy

3.3 Preliminary Sizing of the Fuel-Cell-System

The sizing process for the fuel cell system (FCS) is, as performed for the H2ICE, namely based on simulation. To preserve the consistency of the sizing process, one of the driving cycles used to estimate the H2 consumption of the ICE was used to simulate the FCS-based powertrain.

An important methodological difference between the H2ICE and the FCS is that the FCS could be easier scaled. This is critical for the success of this project, given the low availability of this technology in the market, since it increases the number of commercial FCS that can be used in the ALL-IN Zero project. Therefore, the sizing process of the FCS is mainly based on looking for the best design around that of a commercially available vehicle, thus ensuring the feasibility of the design. The Hyundai XCIENT FCV was taken as a reference, having 2 FCS, of which each stack has a maximum power output of 120 kW, and a system composed of several battery packs with a total energy storage capacity of 73.2 kWh. These components were integrated together with an e-motor with a maximum power of 340 kW and a maximum torque capacity of 4000 Nm (Figure 14). The control strategy for the powertrain was based on the Pontryagin's Minimum Principle, which states that the optimal solution for a given time-dependent problem will be that offering the optimal behavior at each time step. All the simulations were carried out under the battery charge-sustaining operation mode of the vehicle, thus representing a restrictive case in which the H2 consumption would increase compared to other charge-depleting strategies.

Figure 14: FCS-based powertrain outline.

Prior to the simulation of the vehicle in driving cycle conditions, the FC stack model was validated with data from the literature and the BoP designed around it, following the methodology in [1, 2]. From this data, the considered FC stack can provide 20 kW of power each 80 cells with an active surface area of 250 cm². This may be representative of a FC stack for automotive application, but the number of cells per kW could be decreased if, in the experimental activities in WP7, the FC can reach higher current densities. In this case the maximum current density was limited to 1.3 A/cm², close to the limiting current density of 1.44 A/cm² for stability reasons.

Applying this methodology led to the FCS efficiency distribution in Figure 15 after the optimization of the air management strategy. The efficiency evolution was purposely expressed as a function of the current density for scalability purposes. In this graph, the maximum system power output is 97.3 kW and is defined as the FC stack electrical power output minus the power consumption of the BoP components. Since the system is assumed to be scalable for the preliminary sizing, the overall power distribution and cathode mass flow in Figure 15 and Figure 16 are scaled with the maximum FC stack power when it is changed. In this sense, the baseline design was based on the Hyundai XCIENT FCV with a maximum FC stack power output of 120 kW for each FCS, but it was scaled up and down to 140 kW (280 kW in total) and 100 kW (200 kW in total) to understand the impact on consumption and provide a range on the H2 consumption, rather than a fixed value to size the CMR.

Figure 15: FCS efficiency distribution for the baseline stack power of 120 kW.

Analogous to the data provided for the H2ICE, the steady-state optimization also allowed to identify the cathode exhaust mass flow (Figure 16) and the cathode and coolant outlet temperature (Figure 17).

Figure 16: Cathode exhaust mass flow as a function of the FC stack current density.

Figure 17: Cathode and cooling temperature at the outlet of the FC stack as a function of the FC stack current density.

Each one of these designs (2x100 kW to 2x140 kW) were simulated with the aforementioned driving cycles with different levels of FCS dynamics, defined by the maximum value the rate of change of the current density can adopt ($|di/dt|_{max}$). Limiting the dynamics of the FCS is critical, particularly in the heavy-duty vehicle application, to preserve the life of the FC stack as much as possible. This methodology was already carried out by some of the partners in previous studies for light-duty vehicles [3, 4]. The level of dynamics were set to $|di/dt|_{max} \leq 0.1 \text{ A/cm}^2\text{s}$ (high dynamics) and $|di/dt|_{max} \leq 0.01 \text{ A/cm}^2\text{s}$ (moderate dynamics).

As an example, the power evolution along the driving cycle simulation of the e-motor (demand) and the FCS (supply) and the battery (supply and regenerative braking) can be seen for the 140 kW design with different levels of dynamics in Figure 18 and Figure 19.

Figure 18: Evolution of the FCS, battery and e-motor power in the driving cycle simulation with a $|di/dt|_{max} < 0.1 \text{ A/cm}^2\text{s}$.

Figure 19: Evolution of the FCS, battery and e-motor power in the driving cycle simulation with a $|di/dt|_{max} < 0.01 \text{ A/cm}^2\text{s}$.

As it can be seen, the dynamics are higher the less restricted the control strategy is. Therefore, since the optimization aim is to minimize H₂ consumption, this implies that the higher the FCS dynamics the lower the H₂ consumption, thus signifying the trade-off between the performance and the durability. The results in terms of H₂ consumption can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of the driving cycle simulations with the FCS-based powertrain.

	FCS 120+120 kW		FCS 140+140 kW		FCS 100+100 kW	
$ di/dt _{max} \text{ [A/cm}^2\text{s]}$	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.01
Average cons. [g/s]	2.06	2.13	2.00	2.06	2.22	2.27
Max. cons [g/s]	3.26	3.26	3.62	3.81	2.72	2.72
Average cons. [kg/h]	7.42	7.67	7.19	7.42	7.98	8.18
Max. cons [kg/h]	11.75	11.75	13.05	13.70	9.79	9.79

These data can be used to identify both the average and the peak H₂ consumption of the FCS-based powertrain for the HD application. Given the significant increase in the H₂ consumption of the 100+100 kW design, this configuration will most likely be discarded in future stages of the project. However, it is still valid for the heavy-duty vehicle since it can power the e-motor together with the battery while fulfilling the charge-sustaining condition. This leaves a range of average H₂ consumption between 7.19 and 7.67 kg/h to be achieved by the CMR. The peak consumption will be used to size the intermediate H₂ tank, acting as a buffer, when the overall modeling platform is defined.

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